

STRATEGIC PLANNING, ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING, SCHOOL CULTURE, AND PRODUCTIVITY OF PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Strategic Planning, Organizational Learning, School Culture, and Productivity of Private Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract

Institutions face multitude of uncertainties in today's environment, especially in the education sector. This study aimed to determine the influence of strategic planning, organizational learning, and school culture to the productivity of heads-of office in private higher education institutions in Cagayan de Oro City to be equipped with best models in dealing with stakeholders. The study used descriptive correlational and causal-comparative design. 170 respondents are currently holding key positions in the selected private higher education institutions in Cagayan de Oro City. A researcher's made survey questionnaire was the tool used for data gathering to identify the level of influence, performance, and engagement towards productivity. Results revealed that the identified levels were highly influential, performed, and engaged, respectively. When dealing with productivity of the heads-of-offices, it showed that hypothesized model 3 is the best fit. It is concluded that school culture and organizational learning still play important roles in the educational institutions and has emerged as a research subject which requires detailed examination. It is recommended that concerned individuals may lead to develop career opportunities, provide best strategies for employee opportunities, and build workforce connections into the general higher education institution system leading to realistic career opportunities based on workforce needs.

Keywords: *strategic planning, organizational learning, school culture, productivity*

Introduction

Institutions face a multitude of uncertainties in today's environment of shifting resources, especially in the education sector. Mismanaged employees especially the faculty or instructors, personal problems affecting work, political agenda in administration, and the likes result to high turnover rating in the education sector, whether its public or private schools.

Productivity in the organizational learning (OL) has been identified in business administration and management studies over the past forty years as a means of growth, efficiency, and competitive advantage for organizations. OL has a specific status in strategic management research. Broadly, OL aims to explain organizational changes that promote strategic renewal (Lee et al., 2015). This perspective assigns causal importance to linkages between cognition and action and vice versa, which are manifested at many organizational levels. However, organization learning has been used as a general idea rather than a theoretical framework used to analyze the development of a strategy. Consequently, research that involves strategic issues and uses the OL perspective remains underdeveloped. This is due to the struggles that blurs the learning perspective in the strategic research agenda.

This controversy is now considered somewhat overstated. For instance, organizational learning reveals elasticity between interpretative and action-oriented schema. In the same vein, the multi-paradigmatic view of organizational learning. Yet, it is suggested that the strategy-as-practice (s-a-p) agenda should advance toward the knowledge processes and cognitive aspects of the strategy tools in use. Some strategic tools enable people to analyze and generate new knowledge (Belmondo et al., 2015). It was being argued that organizations are processes of becoming. Also, strategy is not an isolated part of organizations. From the cognitive perspective and practice approach, here represented by s-a-p, strategic formulation and implementation are best conceptualized as a set of complex flows across people, activities, and sensing, which means strategizing. This dynamic implies organization learning, which involves strategic renewal.

In a time of major budget reductions in human service organizations (HSOs), there is even more call for demonstrating the difference that comes with services provided. If HSOs wish to stay in business and be competitive, there will be more pressure to demonstrate outcomes.

Setiawan, et al. (2021) mentioned that the involvement of the management does not indicate that the subordinate determines what is achieved or not because the final judgment remains the duty of the chief. It is the mechanism of decision-making shared by representatives of the party. This is the style of leadership that contributes to what is referred to as objective management. The representative leadership style has multiple benefits, one of it mentions that subordinates who engaged in establishing priorities and decision-making freely recognize. Any of the programs and their ability can even be utilized by subordinates. Better choices should be made in this situation. In reality, in Local Universities and Colleges (LUCs), this leadership strategy is genuinely implemented and can assert management advantages through goals.

The study has a practical as well as an academic/theoretical application, with relatively limited exploration of strategic planning, organizational learning, and school culture that has been done in the field of social work. The literature on productivity leans heavily towards pointing out the benefit of an organization's success in improving performance if the organization is, in fact, learning.

For this study, school district size is further defined according to the management process. In small school districts, superintendents can supervise personnel individually from the central office to the classroom level. While one or more levels of management may exist, it is not necessary to use a middle manager to accomplish routine management activities. Medium school districts are managed through one level of management, and large school districts are managed through two or more levels of management.

Many managers in the organization are not able to deal with all the factors that may influence employees' commitment to the organization. There are some unchangeable reasons that managers cannot control. For instance, when the broad environment is prosperous and provides plenty of employment opportunities for people to choose from, the cost to change jobs will be lower, and then it is very likely that people's continuance commitment will decrease. Although there is not so much that the organizations can do about such an unchangeable situation, they can endeavor to make people want to stay with the organization – that is to say, to enhance their affective commitment. Taken altogether, such assertions reinforce Marshall's view, which claims that cognitive and practical approaches can be reconciled. In the same vein, Kump et al. (2015), recognize that organization learning involves the interplay between cognition, practices, and social mechanisms. In this view, OL seems like an "accordion" involving organizational multi-levels like individuals, groups, and the organization itself, and situated activities. This means that OL does not exclude situated activities where the organizational multi-level is packed, and practice is placed at the foreground. Despite this conception, studies addressing multi-level OL and strategic activities are still scarce. This gap is considered and asked about how strategy making is related to organization learning.

Maslow's Needs Hierarchy Theory (1943) argued that survival needs must be satisfied before the individual can satisfy the higher needs. The higher up the hierarchy, the more difficult it is to satisfy the needs associated with that stage, because of the interpersonal and environmental barriers that inevitably frustrate us. Higher needs become increasingly psychological and long-term rather than physiological and short-term, as in the lower survival-related needs (McLeod, S., 2023).

This theory was proposed by proposed by management theorist Douglas McGregor in 1957. Theory X and Y is a combined employee motivation theory that assumes that there are two categories of employees based upon their level of motivation and the most effective approach motivating them. As part of Theory X and Theory Y, managers must be able to motivate employees. Importantly, different types of employees are motivated by different sorts of rewards. Theory X and Theory Y assume that management is required to coordinate all aspects of the value delivery process to be productive (Gordon, J., 2023).

American psychologist Burrhus Frederic Skinner or B.F. Skinner (1957) was best known for his groundbreaking theories on behavior and Ivan Pavlov (1903). Along with his associates, Skinner proposed the Reinforcement Theory of Motivation. Its main idea is that positive consequences dictate productive behavior. According to this team productivity theory, employees who get a reward after doing something positive would have enough encouragement to push themselves more. This is so they keep receiving positive feedback. On the other hand, if you do not positively react to an employee's good performance, it's unlikely for them to have the drive to do well again. Based on this theory, a person's future behaviors can be changed by the consequences imposed by the external environment. To increase desired behavior, reward it with a pleasant stimulus or remove an aversive stimulus when it happens. To decrease undesired behavior, give an aversive stimulus or remove a pleasant stimulus after it occurs (Li, P., 2023).

This study is a contribution to the field of human services management as well as to business and management by measuring the process of productivity within higher education institutions. It also contributes to social work education and macro social work practice by examining a largely business and management concept and applying it to the field of social work.

Research Questions

The key research questions for this research study are:

1. What is the level of strategic planning in terms of:
 - 1.1. risk management;
 - 1.2. engagement; and
 - 1.3. evaluation?
2. What is the level of organizational learning in terms of:
 - 2.1. culture;
 - 2.2. facilitation; and
 - 2.3. performance management?
3. What is the level of school culture in terms of:
 - 3.1. nurturing environment;
 - 3.2. sense of responsibility; and
 - 3.3. commitment to lifelong learning?
4. What is the level of productivity of higher education institutions in terms of:
 - 4.1. leadership; and
 - 4.2. capacity resources?
5. Is there a significant relationship between productivity of higher education institutions and:

- 5.1. strategic planning;
- 5.2. organizational learning; and
- 5.3. school culture?
6. Which among the variables, singly or in combination, influence the productivity of higher education institutions?
7. What causal model best fit productivity of higher education institutions?

Literature Review

Strategic Planning

Westhuizen (2017) mentioned that several approaches may be utilized to measure the impact of an organization strategy and business plan. Mostly, benchmarking, Gap, SWOT, and pest analysis are the commonly used tools for evaluation. The Gap technique involves measuring an organization's current position to that of its desired level. It is used in a variety of aspects of business such as profits, production, market share, and the strength of a brand. The SWOT analysis examines a firm's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in relation to other players in the market.

Moreover, Asikhia (2021) mentioned in a study that the identified a number of reasons why management planning is considered critical to the success of any management. Firstly, they opined that management planning provides direction to managers and non-managers as well. The scholars reported that if all members of an organization, irrespective of their cadre, have a clear-cut understanding of the goals an organization is seeking to achieve and what it would take to achieve it, they would cooperate with one another to ensure that the vision is attained.

In essence, none of these listed activities can be successfully executed and measured without adequate and effective planning. The authors identified that numerous studies have researched the concept of management planning and reported the existence of a positive relationship between planning and performance. It was further reported that positive financial reports are largely associated with well-drawn management plans. A positive relationship was also reported between management planning, improved profits, higher return on investments and several other positive organizational success or growth indicators (Omojola et al., 2021).

Risk Management

The basic element of this system can determine the risk assessment stage, this stage is a comprehensive basis for launching the subsequent iteration of the entire risk management cycle. Naturally, in the absence of the ability to identify and identify the risk, it is impossible to carry out all further work to manage it. Identification and risk analysis being the basis for the management system, however, in essence, they are not the stages that can be considered the foundation of the system, which we will call the basis of the risk management culture. Systematization of risks in order to further manage them is what determines the basis of a risk management culture. The diverse nature of risks is predetermined by the nature of this phenomenon, and of course for each business entity, this diversity will be formed on the basis of external and internal environmental factors in which it operates (Filyppova et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the diverse nature of risks is predetermined by the nature of this phenomenon, and of course for each business entity, this diversity will be formed on the basis of external and internal environmental factors in which it operates. Before moving on to the issue of systematization, people should dwell on the issue of risk classification. As already noted, risks can be divided into external and internal, but such a division is too general for such a complex economic category (Prodanova et al., 2019).

Additionally, identification and risk analysis being the basis for the management system, however, in essence, they are not the stages that can be considered the foundation of the system, which we will call the basis of the risk management culture. Systematization of risks in order to further manage them is what determines the basis of a risk management culture (Filyppova et al., 2019).

Engagement

Lee and Esen (2017) stated that two major themes emerged repeatedly throughout their investigation of the leading contributors to job satisfaction and employee engagement. These are "fairness and openness," which are regarded as essential components for any organization's structural soundness. They serve as the foundation of any institution while also permeating every policy and process..." They went on to say that failing to integrate these components is a missed opportunity that demonstrates apathy and impedes the employee-employer relationship. Although it is unrealistic to avoid all negative circumstances, employees are more willing to accept the conditions or outcomes if they believe the process or policy is based on reasonable terms. For any organization to thrive and inspire continuous success, equality and transparency must be evident from the top down and the bottom up.

Moreover, Navajas-Romero (2022) claims that the role of work engagement and teamwork performance as a mediator in the study of sustainable human resource management. The current study aims to analyze the properties of the working conditions recorded in the Sixth European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS); with it, seven independent indexes about different aspects of work quality in the health sector have been constructed, and these constructs are used to evaluate their effects on work engagement (WE). The novelty of incorporating teamwork as a modulating variable is included in this sense. The study is about how prospects, social environment, intensity, and earnings all influence work commitment, which is related to job performance. For the development of truly sustainable Human Resources policies, knowledge of the determinants of work commitment and the ability to modulate its effects in teamwork

environments is required.

Evaluation

For the results of evaluation under current conditions, 75% of school administrations meet the NSE. The challenge is a) Develop the vision, mission and objectives of the school with an accountable mechanism and in accordance with the NSE then implement it in all educational activities in the school. b) Partner with relevant parties that can encourage the rapid process of quality education, such as departments, government agencies, law enforcement, social and non-governmental organizations, as well as companies that are committed to Education. c) Create a conducive and friendly learning environment in the midst of heterogeneous and compound settlements. d) Carry out quality education services and evaluation of class action research at least once a year (Pitriantini et al., 2020).

In evaluation, improvement efforts to achieve quality education not only fulfill the input and output aspects, but more importantly the process aspect, which is in question is decision making, program management, institutional management process, teaching learning process and monitoring and evaluation process with the note that the teaching learning process has the highest level of interest compared to other processes. Therefore, from the results of the research that has been done, state school has a strategic analysis and a quality recommendation for improving the national standard of education (Permana et al., 2020).

Moreover, it is essential in determining how best to use resources and take advantage of strengths and opportunities to combat the threats and weaknesses. The PEST analysis is critical in the evaluation of the environmental factors that may affect a venture. It examines the political, economic, social and technological aspects that influence business strategies. Pest analysis helps to talk about the outside forces that are beyond an agency's control. Lastly, benchmarking examines the extent that a firm has attained compared to the final objective. In that case it talks more about how far a venture needs to go (Anna, 2015).

Organizational Learning

Implementing knowledge management process in any organizations is essential, as it enhances organizational learning capabilities and problem resolution skills of individual and group of employees. Thus, it seems plausible, that these competences and skills will support employees in adequately performing their job. We therefore presume that knowledge management process can provide specific resources that are available to employees. The job demands-resources model suggests that these elements positively affect employees' engagement (Cesário et al., 2017).

Studies stated that high work commitment is strongly related to organizational performance. Work commitment has an impact on all organizations on some level and enables organizations to evaluate issues such as turnover during times of fluctuating financial solidity. These mentalities work together to shape the theoretical framework of each individual's work duty (Redmond, 2016).

Furthermore, recent studies on critical attitudinal antecedents of firm performance highlight a positive relation between a work-commitment environment and a sharing knowledge culture as being a strong predictor of individual performance. It is possible that organizational commitment contributes to knowledge sharing by improving people's perceptions about the organization (Cabrera et al., 2006 as mentioned by Chambel et al., 2017).

Culture

Employee diversity has also been identified as a factor influencing employee productivity in studies. Kiura (2018) stated that informal social networks made up of people from different cultures are a common occurrence in the workplace, but little is known about their impact on employee productivity. As a result, some organizational leaders believe that these networks have negative consequences for an organization. The study, on the other hand, indicates that networks contribute positively to employee productivity. Managers should pay attention to other factors, such as employee diversity, which can impede employee productivity while also encouraging informal interactions. As a result, managers should value employee diversity, recognize the value of in-group identities, and use them to foster a positive work environment.

Bhat (2019) mentioned that "a committed team of employees is an organization's dream come true." A dedicated team of employees is best for an organization's or any business's long-term future. It is the responsibility of the organization's leaders to create that culture. Job satisfaction boosts productivity. Committed employees require a leader who will guide them, not someone who must be constantly behind them back to get the job done. Such organizational commitment leads to increased workplace productivity. A compliant team will create tasks and ensure that they are completed. They will arrive at work on time and complete all necessary tasks.

Additionally, employee diversity has also been identified as a factor influencing employee productivity in studies. Kiura (2018) stated that informal social networks made up of people from different cultures are a common occurrence in the workplace, but little is known about their impact on employee productivity. As a result, some organizational leaders believe that these networks have negative consequences for an organization.

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Facilitation

Pry (2016) highlighted that when the organizational structure supports self-determination in the workplace, job satisfaction and employee commitment to the organization increase, with benefits accruing to both the organization and the employee. Similarly, job satisfaction is generated by an environment that involves employees in decision-making, such as giving them some say over the design of their jobs at the individual level, or participation at the organizational level, such as strategic planning, restructuring, and other participatory activities.

Short (2015), on the other hand, focused on leaders' notes that practices aimed at fostering job satisfaction and organizational commitment. High Leader-Organization Fit may also have a positive impact on leader retention. Improving job satisfaction and organizational commitment will reduce the likelihood of turnover. The incorporation of Leader-Organization Fit assessments into leader selection and professional development practices is expected to increase job satisfaction and organizational commitment in leaders, reducing turnover intentions. When employees experience high levels of fit, it is expected that they will perceive their jobs as more secure, as they will recognize that the organizations are unlikely to terminate the relationships when their needs are met.

Performance Management

Shayegan, Yavari, and Bazrkar (2022) stated that human resource development practices are focused on the organization's specific goals, what needs to be done, and the change that needs to be implemented. Training and development, employee involvement, and professional development are the most important and effective methods of human resource development. Employees of the organization made this observation. Because transformational leadership is one of the prerequisites for the development of service organizations, applying this leadership style in the organization, as well as implementing effective measures and practices such as training with an individual development approach and employee participation, organizational performance can be improved.

Additionally, Ghafoor, R., Khan, G., Khan, M. (2021) stated in the study entitled "Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance" training and development, on-the-job training, training design, and delivery style are emphasized as four of the most important aspects in organizational studies. The current study seeks to comprehend the impact of Training and Development, On-the-Job Training, Training Design, and Training Delivery Style on organizational performance. According to the research, all of these have a significant impact on organizational performance. The findings indicate that Training and Development, On-the-Job Training, Training Design, and Delivery Style all have a significant impact on Organizational Performance, and all have a positive impact. It means that it improves overall organizational performance.

Colby (2017) stated that millennial generation workers may require different managerial motivation techniques than more senior workers due to the unique perspectives and values that this cohort brings to the workplace. Management's ability to understand and motivate Millennials is challenged by their sense of security, lack of experience with failure, and attitudes toward teamwork, achievement, recognition, and leisure. Formal awards (established professional or competitive programs) and informal recognition (public or private informal praise) in the workplace are perceived by Millennial Generation employees, and whether such awards and recognition motivate them to achieve high levels of work performance. Managers should understand the positive impact of awards and recognition programs on all employees, that recognition does not appeal to all employees for the same reasons, that some employees prefer regular, direct feedback from supervisors, and that Millennials want to understand the awards and recognition process and decisions. Individual organizations award and recognize employees based on their needs, allowing the program to have the greatest impact.

School Culture

Individuals adjust to their environments with the help of their acquired social and emotional skills that play a crucial role in their lives. The importance of socio-emotional skills has risen significantly because it contributes to the well-being not just of individuals, but of the whole community and in an increasingly transforming and diverse world (Chernyshenko et al., 2018).

A shared set of moral beliefs, a reliance and a sense of responsibility, appreciation of employees and commemoration of achievement are all attributed to Student performance. Culture affects all aspects of an educational institution and it influences informal conversations between students (Deal & Peterson, 2016).

Finally, the central objective of attending or working in a school would be to boost the ability of a person, and that is why researchers say that school is one of the most important settings for the acquisition of skills. While school time can be enjoyable, it can also enhance social relationships and social consciousness. Missing school, even for a short while, will have consequences for skill development (Burgess & Sievertsen, 2020).

Nurturing Environment

Agarwal (2018) mentioned that by developing robust models to understand environmental trends and forecast how current unchecked practices will affect the natural environment, data scientists can present a well-reasoned, quantitative analysis and inspire people to be more engaged in sustainable and environment-friendly practices. Data scientists are uniquely poised to harness the power of patterns and tell compelling stories about nature.

Notably, the relationship between development and environment gave birth to the sustainable development concept, whose central idea is that global ecosystems and humanity itself can be threatened by neglecting the environment. Scholars have observed that since environmental economists are concerned that the long-term neglect of the environmental assets is likely to jeopardize the durability of economic growth, and sustainable development therefore “involves maximizing the net benefits of economic development, subject to maintaining the services and quality of natural resources over time.” Its concern is about balancing the objectives of economic growth and attending to environmental considerations. Sustainable development aims to improve the quality of life in a comprehensive manner, including economic prosperity, social equity and environmental protection. Economic, social, environmental and cultural aspects must be integrated in a harmonious manner to enhance the intergenerational well-being (Muigua, 2017).

Sense of Responsibility

Lowe, et al. (2016) hypothesized there are seven variables, or predictors, that influence the extent of a firm’s Corporate Responsibility (CR) in an Australian bus operator context; and industry composed of virtually all small, medium, and large trans-generational family firms. These are: firm size; operator type; operator location; residence of operator; form of service contract; social capital linkage between the operator and their voluntary professional association; and Sense of Community (SOC), as measured by the Sense of Community Index (SOC). The SOC was used to examine what is, and what is not, important to firms about being part of a community.

Nowell and Boyd (2014) developed a tool to measure a complementary, but unique aspect of the experience of community. Where SOC emphasizes community as a resource and a predictor of general participation in a community, SOCR emphasizes the experience of community as a responsibility. The authors developed a variant of the SOC to examine the sense of community found in community collaborations. These are defined as groups of leaders from organizations, agencies, and community groups who meet regularly. They expect measures emphasizing responsibility for a community to have a stronger direct association to indices of engagement and leadership relative to models that emphasize perceptions of community as a resource.

Commitment to Lifelong Learning

Training courses are most effective when they are tailored for specific roles and at identifiable career inflection points, as opposed to being offered episodically, according to the calendar, or when HR secures resources for new learning initiatives. Senior executives will play a major role in a company’s attitude toward learning. They can start making the case for lifelong employability by sharing what they know about the changing work and economic landscape. A first principle of learning is that people learn what they want to learn. Leaders, therefore, need to communicate the imperative to inspire employees toward a mind-set of continuous skill improvement. As is so often the case, inspiration starts at the top: leaders need to be role models and show that they value learning themselves (Davies et al., 2019).

Furthermore, Cesário et al. (2017) mentioned in a study that there was a model of organizational commitment that conceptualizes commitment as consisting of three components: affective, normative and calculative. Affective commitment refers to a positive feeling of affection towards the organization as reflected in a strong desire to remain and a feeling of pride in being part of the organization. Normative commitment reflects a moral feeling or obligation to continue in the organization. Employees with high levels of the normative component feel that they ought to remain, and they feel bad about leaving the organization even if a new employment opportunity appears. Calculative commitment reflects an intention to remain in the organization because leaving would have tremendous negative effects in terms of costs to the employee. Research shows that these three commitment components are related to employees’ work and outcomes, and employees with good performance who are focused on the business are critical to the success of an organization. Some previous studies have reported a significant association between organizational commitment and employee performance.

Productivity

A study by Egdair, et al. (2020) stated that organizational performance refers to the ability of each organization to achieve its objectives regarding the quality of service provided. To the beneficiaries and high profit makers, a significant share in the rival market, and the results of high-income money in a stock market, enable the organization to survive. To explain further, predefined strategy means working from different systems and strong foundations that can reach the featured performer. Furthermore, seven areas of OP are identified; effectiveness, productivity, quality, customer satisfaction, stakeholders, efficiency, and innovation.

Moreover, Vijayvargy, & Agarwal (2014) stated that the OP is the standard by which the index is evaluated. As discussed above, performance measurement is one of the threads that are often discussed. It is necessary to understand and clarify the meaning to be more pronounced. However, the performance measurement work is described, where it indicates that quantitative measurement, is linked directly to work (Shen, Chen, & Wang, 2016).

Leadership

Benjamin, et al. (2022) stated that improved team function and performance are associated with leadership, supportive team behavior, communication, and performance feedback across various sectors. Addressing the reported challenges and considering the importance of organizational commitment to team development can help ensure that team objectives are effectively designed, delivered, and sustained in the context of complex sporting organizations where leaders must respond to multiple stakeholders and meet performance

goals across multiple dimensions of effectiveness. It is widely acknowledged that team function dynamics are important for high-performance sport outcomes; however, there is a lack of evidence to provide guidance in the high-performance sport context; thus, we have investigated teamwork in other sectors.

Moreover, Black (2023) stated that the study of mentorship models in veterans' affairs hospital pre-doctoral training emphasized that mentorship of doctoral level psychology interns may provide an opportunity to aid in the MISSION Act's retention efforts. The purpose of this study was to look into the differences in retention rates between VA internships that offer Formal Mentorship Programs (FMPs) and VA internships that do not offer FMPs (mentorship via supervision only). The relationship between the total domains of formal mentoring (communication, mentoring process, mentee development, mentor, program efficacy) and retention was also evaluated. The findings show that there is no significant difference in retention rates between VA sites (FMP vs. no FMP) and that there is no significant relationship between the number of FMP domains and retention. According to a thorough convergent analysis, the inherent nature of FMPs may exacerbate identified turnover factors such as perceived bureaucracy and burnout.

Additionally, Clarke (2018) found that higher levels of employee perception of the quality of management in the workplace are associated with higher levels of intrinsic motivation. Suggests that higher levels of perceived managerial quality by employees are associated with higher levels of identified regulation- both autonomous motivations significantly support employee innovative work output via the causal mediation of employee innovative work behavior. Work ethics may reflect identified regulation and thus confound the relationship between perceptions of management quality and identified regulation.

Capacity Resources

Dugovicova (2019) stated that globalization environment has resulted in a better choice of employment and benefits. Managers' roles in motivating and retaining employees are becoming increasingly difficult in an age of constant change. In general, if the manager fails in the motivation process and is unable to provide any stimulus to the work environment, the employee will be dissatisfied. Satisfaction is closely related to motivation, and disgruntled employees' work attitude can lead to stagnation and, later, employment change, which has a negative impact on the company's total wage costs, training and recruitment costs, and, in some cases, the disclosure of know-how to competitors.

In addition, the Association for Talent Development (2021) discovered that companies that provide comprehensive training programs earn 218 percent more per employee than companies that do not provide formalized training. But it does not end there. These businesses also have a 24% higher profit margin than those that spend less on training. It appears that continuing to invest in training and development, even during economic downturns, is a wise move. Increased employee productivity, which is driven by skill advancements made possible through employee training and development, is at the heart of these fantastic results.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive correlational and causal-comparative design. Descriptive correlational design aims to answer the question "How are things related?" It involves gathering data through surveys or observational methods to examine the relationships between variables (Dulock, 2023). Causal-comparative research is an attempt to identify a causative relationship between an independent variable and a dependent variable. The relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable is usually a suggested relationship, not proven, because you, the researcher, do not have complete control over the independent variable (Maheshwari, 2018).

Respondents

Respondents are currently employed in the education sector in the different schools in Cagayan de Oro City, who may not handle the same position/s. The researcher conducted a stratified random sampling which involves handpicking of the respondents, usually to suit very specific intentions that could come up with the result on determining the subject matter.

A stratified random sampling was employed. The researcher employed the Raosoft Formula to get the sample from the total population of 301. Breakdown of respondents are: 34 for Capitol University, 20 for Cagayan de Oro College, 11 for Golden Heritage Polytechnic College, 23 for Southern de Oro Philippines College, 20 for Pilgrim Christian College, 22 for STI College, 11 for Blessed Mother College, 14 for AMA Computer College, and 15 for Informatics Institute-Cagayan de Oro. A total of 170 actual respondents in the study were randomly selected employing face-to-face visit in conducting the survey. Before the respondents started answering the questionnaires, the researcher discussed first the details of the instrument. Concerns and clarifications from the respondents about the questionnaire were answered directly by the researcher while waiting for the respondents to finish.

Instrument

The instrument was a researcher's made survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was constructed with several parts. The first part details the level of influence on the factors in strategic planning in schools in term of risk management; engagement; and evaluation. Next part details the level of performance on the factors in organizational learning in terms of culture; facilitation; and performance management. Third part details the level of engagement on school culture in terms of nurturing environment; sense of responsibility;

and commitment to lifelong learning. The final part investigates the level of productivity of higher education institutions in terms of leadership and capacity resources.

The instrument responded to a five-point Likert's Scale of (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) Neutral, (2) Disagree, (1) Strongly Disagree.

Procedure

The responses were coded, tallied, and collated in tables for purposes of statistical treatment and data analysis. For the independent variables, proper scaling was also be used. To complete the 86-item questionnaire, it took the respondents approximately 15 to 20 minutes to answer.

Part 1 of the questionnaire had a scoring scale of twenty-four (24) items that measures level of influence on strategic planning in terms of risk management, engagement, and evaluation.

Part 2 of the questionnaire had a scoring scale of twenty-three (23) items that measures level of performance on organizational learning in terms of culture, facilitation, and performance management.

Part 3 of the questionnaire had a scoring scale of twenty-five (25) items that measures level of engagement on school culture in terms of nurturing environment, sense of responsibility, and commitment to lifelong learning.

Part 4 of the questionnaire had a scoring scale of fourteen (14) items that measures level of productivity of private higher education institutions in terms of leadership and capacity resources.

Ethical Considerations

The manuscript had undergone content validity from the experts in the field to ensure quality. Adhering to the critical procedures of research ethics and receiving approval from the Research Ethics Review Committee, the methods of data collection strictly adhered to the proper course of action. All procedures and requirements were followed in order to finally present the data to the adviser and research panel for binding approval.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered and the analyses as well as its interpretation. The answers are presented based on the sequence of the problem stated. For the modes of analyses on problems number 1, 2, 3, and 4, descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and their corresponding interpretations were used to present the data on (1) the level of influence on the strategic planning, (2) the level of performance on the organizational learning, (3) the level of engagement on the school culture, and (4) level of productivity of higher education institutions. With regards to the significant relationship of the variables, Pearson's Correlation was used to gather relevant results for problem number 5. For problem number 6, Multiple Regression was used to which among the variables, singly or in combination, influence the productivity of higher education institutions. For problem number 7, Path Analysis Model was used to which statistical method best fit productivity of selected higher education institutions.

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Strategic Planning in Terms of Risk Management

Risk Management	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution demonstrates the importance of ethical values and integrity through their directives, attitudes and behavior.	4.34	0.76	Highly Influential
2. The institution has established standards of conduct and has clearly communicated expectations at all levels throughout the department.	4.27	0.69	Highly Influential
3. The performance of individuals and departments are evaluated at least annually to ensure adherence to the institution's standards of conduct.	4.03	0.82	Highly Influential
4. The institution takes seriously variations from standards and has implemented clear policies and procedures to ensure that these types of behaviors are dealt with consistently and timely.	4.02	0.63	Highly Influential
5. The institution routinely reviews and provides input for deficiencies related to the design, implementation, and maintenance of the school's system of internal controls taking into account the potential for risk.	4.05	0.61	Highly Influential
6. The institution has a system in place to communicate and receive input from stakeholders' and further evaluate the potential impact on achieving its objectives.	3.86	0.65	Highly Influential
7. The institution has established and evaluates periodically the lines of performing to enable execution of authorities and responsibilities and the flow of information to manage the activities of the department.	4.09	0.62	Highly Influential
8. The responsibilities and delegation of authority have been appropriately assigned and appear to be clearly understood and observed by employees throughout the institution.	4.23	0.70	Highly Influential

9. Written documentation exists covering the institution's internal control structure and for all significant events. They are readily available for its intended students and other personnel.	4.16	0.74	Highly Influential
10. Training opportunities are available and are encouraged for both new and existing employees to develop the knowledge and skills required to perform their duties to the institutional.	4.45	3.95	Highly Influential
Overall	4.15	1.02	Highly Influential

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Strategic Planning in Terms of Engagement

Engagement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution encourages all departments to have a dynamic community of learners.	4.60	0.64	Very Highly Influential
2. The institution ensures all employees to be dedicated to academic excellence.	4.49	0.66	Highly Influential
3. The institution ensures all employees to be dedicated to high quality research.	4.20	0.69	Highly Influential
4. The institution encourages all employees to embrace rules of excellence in education.	4.48	0.70	Highly Influential
5. The institution is committed to embrace tradition of excellence in education.	4.51	0.70	Very Highly Influential
6. Employees are encouraged to address the intellectual and cultural needs of ever-evolving local society.	4.13	0.82	Highly Influential
Overall	4.40	0.70	Highly Influential

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Strategic Planning in Terms of Evaluation

Evaluation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution is keen to honest evaluation towards its employees.	4.39	0.71	Highly Influential
2. The institution encourages semestral/annual evaluation of employees for the betterment of work performance.	4.32	0.63	Highly Influential
3. The institution holds fair evaluation of employees on whatever level they belong.	4.30	0.74	Highly Influential
4. The institution assures that the evaluation maintains confidentiality towards its results.	4.36	0.66	Highly Influential
5. The institution designates right office handling evaluation of employees.	4.34	0.64	Highly Influential
6. The institution is dedicated to conduct fair evaluation in every aspect of work maintaining company standards.	4.22	0.69	Highly Influential
7. The institution compiles all pertinent data with regards to the security and confidentiality of documents.	4.39	0.68	Highly Influential
8. The institution is committed to address concerns regarding the evaluation process and its changes for best improvements.	4.44	0.58	Highly Influential
9. The institution assures all stakeholders that evaluation is fair, just, and true to all of its employees.	4.40	0.58	Highly Influential
Overall	4.35	0.66	Highly Influential

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Organizational Learning in Terms of Culture

Culture	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution handles failure well and is open to change (e.g., adapts to setbacks, unexpected developments, mistakes, and failures are openly discussed, etc.).	4.08	0.70	Highly Performed

2. The institution makes time for sharing and reflection (e.g., there is time for brainstorming, debriefs, this time is well facilitated and organized, all relevant staff members are involved etc.).	4.24	0.66	Highly Performed
3. The institution engages outside stakeholders (e.g., there are advisory groups for programs or projects, there is regular contact with partners, etc.).	4.08	0.78	Highly Performed
4. The institution has a culture that values evaluation (e.g., evaluation is part of decision-making, resources are dedicated to evaluation, etc.).	4.41	0.56	Highly Performed
5. The institution emphasizes strong communication (e.g., reports or findings are publicly shared, reports or findings are easy to access, etc.).	4.16	0.64	Highly Performed
6. The institution ensures employer-employee professional relationship for the betterment of the company.	4.41	0.65	Highly Performed
7. The institution handles challenges with utmost professionalism at all times.	4.24	0.61	Highly Performed
8. The institution is keen to deliver best work culture/s to address employee diversity.	4.22	0.52	Highly Performed
Overall	4.23	0.64	Highly Performed

Table 5. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Organizational Learning in Terms of Facilitation

Facilitation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution sets high facilitation standards towards its operations.	3.85	0.70	Highly Performed
2. The institution encourages heads-of-offices to embody progressive mindset towards its employees.	4.15	0.64	Highly Performed
3. The institution encourages heads-of-offices to assist and make improvements easier to its employees.	4.18	0.55	Highly Performed
4. The institution sets designs in helping each of its departments/units meet both departmental and institutional goals.	4.07	0.67	Highly Performed
5. It is the prepares its head-of-office employees to lead with utmost respect to the institution and its stakeholders.	4.32	0.61	Highly Performed
6. Its trainings and seminars are considered an art of improving employee skills and become leaders in the company.	4.06	0.60	Highly Performed
7. The institution sets employees' skills to be used in working with a group, enabling and supporting them to achieve their objectives in a way that involves and respects all contributions.	4.17	0.58	Highly Performed
8. The institution sets employees' skills to build ownership and releases the potential of the group and its members.	4.25	0.55	Highly Performed
Overall	4.13	0.61	Highly Performed

Table 6. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Organizational Learning in Terms of Performance Management

Performance Management	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution ensures that employees know what their goals are and why they matter to the business.	4.38	0.71	Highly Performed
2. The institution ensures that employees have a forum to ask the heads-of-office questions and clarifications.	4.34	0.75	Highly Performed
3. The institution ensures that employees feel appreciated and valued by their heads-of-office.	4.42	0.68	Highly Performed
4. The institution helps heads-of-office scale the performance management efforts of its stakeholders.	4.11	0.62	Highly Performed
5. The institution leads each of the departments and units to invest resources into initiatives and programs that will learn mean little to employees.	4.12	0.67	Highly Performed

6. The institution encourages heads-of-office to conduct semestral and/or annual performance management evaluation to help improve the department as well as the institution itself.	4.14	0.66	Highly Performed
7. The institution encourages heads-of-office to practice fairness and equity of the performance evaluation process.	4.38	0.74	Highly Performed
Overall	4.27	0.69	Highly Performed

Table 7. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on School Culture in Terms of Nurturing Environment

Nurturing Environment	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution's environment maintains high engagement of the strength of social connections between teachers, staff, and students within and beyond the institution.	4.08	0.50	Highly Engaged
2. The institution engages high quality of teaching and amount of learning students experiences and employee development.	4.12	0.58	Highly Engaged
3. Heads of the institution assures development of the overall physical, social, and learning environment of the employees and students.	4.05	0.56	Highly Engaged
4. The institution engages to take meaningful action on school climate improvement, where educators and employees need to understand the thoughts, feelings, and experiences of members of the school community.	4.17	0.64	Highly Engaged
5. Heads-of-office engages in elevating stakeholder voices, where they gain important insights into the lived experiences of stakeholders of the institutions.	4.22	0.55	Highly Engaged
6. The institution engages heads-of-offices important data that can be used to identify areas for growth and plan initiatives and interventions for improving school climate.	3.96	0.73	Highly Engaged
7. The institution practices feedbacking during every semester for the betterment of the office and the whole operation of the institution.	3.98	0.78	Highly Engaged
Overall	4.08	0.62	Highly Engaged

Table 8. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on School Culture in Terms of Sense of Responsibility

Sense of Responsibility	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution utilizes self-reflection and reflective supervision whenever possible during and immediately following an emergency response or front line on-call situation.	4.02	0.61	Highly Engaged
2. The institution ensures that employees are sufficiently orientated and trained and utilize management techniques that make staff feel competent and supported in their jobs.	4.07	0.61	Highly Engaged
3. The heads-of-office regularly encourage staff to take adequate breaks during the course of their workday.	4.38	0.78	Highly Engaged
4. The administration develops a comprehensive plan for staff safety, including personal/work-related security protocols.	4.47	0.62	Highly Engaged
5. The administration looks for ways to build task and client diversity into the employees' work and/or burden. Offer opportunities for job and self-enrichment.	4.41	0.60	Highly Engaged
6. The administration understands that your employees are the most important resource in providing humanitarian services.	4.30	0.71	Highly Engaged
7. The administration uses a parallel process to portray a positive outlook, and to praise employee efforts and successful outcomes.	4.31	0.65	Highly Engaged
8. The administration develops a protocol for how employees will be expected to deal with specific and ongoing jobs and challenges.	4.26	0.62	Highly Engaged
Overall	4.27	0.65	Highly Engaged

Table 10. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on School Culture in Terms of Commitment to Lifelong Learning

Commitment to Lifelong Learning	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The institution as well as the heads-of-office encourages employees to be equipped with the best learnings in life.	4.32	0.52	Highly Engaged
2. The administration engages personally with the employees to finish studies in line with their field of interest.	4.15	0.44	Highly Engaged
3. The institution encourages loyalty among its employees by providing them best experiences in the workplace and sustainable compensation based on their credentials and experiences.	4.20	0.44	Highly Engaged
4. The institution continuously makes changes, according to which will maximally adapt the content and form of educational activities to specific requirements to enhance one's skills and abilities.	4.11	0.45	Highly Engaged
5. The administration formulates training evaluations that focus on employees' expectations before the start of the work which allow them to get a clearer idea on what job they are in to.	4.12	0.57	Highly Engaged
6. The administration assures that employees and other stakeholders in the institution work accordingly base on the vision and mission of the institution and the office/department itself.	4.29	0.54	Highly Engaged
7. The administration assures that as attractive salaries and perks become more commonplace, employees and potential employees are encouraged to focus on the organization's culture and values when performing its work leading to lifelong commitment with the company.	3.96	0.60	Highly Engaged
8. The administration develops a way for head-of-offices to understand the perspectives and ideas of their employees, which can lead to better decision-making, policy-making, and improved employee satisfaction leading to loyalty and eagerness to perform duty.	4.11	0.53	Highly Engaged
9. The head-of-office encourages employees to pursue graduate and post-graduate studies to enhance knowledge and skills, leading to growth and additional compensation.	4.19	0.54	Highly Engaged
10. The administration encourages heads-of-office to examine the impact which the removal of barriers towards employee commitment to clearly understand reasons and formulate intervention.	4.09	0.59	Highly Engaged
Total	4.15	0.52	Highly Engaged

Table 11. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Productivity of Higher Education Institutions in Terms of Leadership

Leadership	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. My department's leadership develops learning goals and processes for individual staff.	4.20	0.64	Highly Productive
2. My department's leadership develops learning goals and processes for teams and projects.	4.51	3.94	Very Highly Productive
3. My department's key learning indicators are identified, learning goals/priorities are included in job descriptions, professional development opportunities are discussed, etc..	4.23	0.52	Highly Productive
4. My department's leadership regularly reviews learning goals and processes with individual staff members and teams.	4.25	0.65	Highly Productive
5. My department's leadership provides opportunities for input (e.g., staff are encouraged to provide feedback, etc.).	4.28	0.62	Highly Productive
6. My department's leadership promotes and rewards learning (e.g., learning achievements are acknowledged, professional development is supported and encouraged, sharing negative feedback is encouraged, etc.).	4.30	0.67	Highly Productive
7. My department leads employees to be committed to work and to take pride in one's work.	4.42	0.63	Highly Productive
Overall	4.31	1.10	Very Highly Productive

Table 12. Mean and Standard Deviation Distribution on Productivity of Higher Education Institutions in Terms of Capacity Resources

Capacity Resources	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. My department has the right tools to organize and manage information in a way that supports learning.	4.08	0.41	Highly Productive
2. My department has the right tools to reflect on and share lessons learned and share with colleagues such as templates, workplans, dashboards, collaborative writing/editing tools, etc..	4.12	0.50	Highly Productive
3. My department has a high degree of staff expertise when it comes to learning such as staff are comfortable with data collection and analysis, evaluation is part of some staff job descriptions, staff are trained in learning from mistakes, etc..	4.09	0.51	Highly Productive
4. My department has adequate resources available to support camaraderie such as professional development opportunities are available to staff, funding is allocated to evaluation, etc..	4.24	0.53	Highly Productive
5. My department has sufficient physical space or encourages staff to use external space to brainstorm, debrief, discuss progress, etc. as needed.	4.11	0.53	Highly Productive
6. My department has the necessary resources and support to fulfill my job responsibilities effectively.	4.17	0.57	Highly Productive
7. My department has adequate resources such as equipment, technology, materials provided to perform job duties effectively.	4.11	0.58	Highly Productive
Overall	4.13	0.52	Highly Productive

Table 13. Pearson's Correlations on the Significant Relationship between Productivity of Higher Education Institutions and Strategic Planning, Organizational Learning, and School Culture

		n	Pearson's r	p-value	Decision on Ho1
Strategic Planning	- Organizational Learning	170	0.30	***	< .001
Strategic Planning	- School Culture	170	0.31	***	< .001
Strategic Planning	- Productivity	170	0.22	**	0.004
Organizational Learning	- School Culture	170	0.63	***	< .001
Organizational Learning	- Productivity	170	0.28	***	< .001
School Culture	- Productivity	170	0.39	***	< .001

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Table 14. Multiple Regression on Which Among the Variables, Singly or in Combination, Influence the Productivity of Higher Education Institutions

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.748	.392		1.909	.058
Risk Management	.061	.062	.072	.991	.323
Engagement	.138	.086	.141	1.596	.112
Evaluation	.096	.104	.091	.926	.356
Culture	-.139	.119	-.123	-1.169	.244
Facilitation	-.040	.133	-.036	-.300	.764
Performance Management	.143	.105	.145	1.366	.174

Nurturing Environment	.358	.110	.339	3.243	.001
Sense of Responsibility	-.696	.147	-.669	-4.734	.000
Commitment to Lifelong Learning	.923	.181	.706	5.102	.000

R=.624* R²=.390 Adjusted R²=.355 F=11.357 P-value=.000

Legend: p<.05 is significant and p>.05 is not significant

Table 15. Regression Weights of Causal Model 1 of Productivity

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PHE	<---	RM	.061	.051	1.200	.230
PHE	<---	EN	.138	.059	2.347	.019
PHE	<---	EV	.096	.063	1.520	.129
PHE	<---	CU	-.139	.068	-2.046	.041
PHE	<---	FA	-.040	.067	-.593	.553
PHE	<---	PM	.143	.059	2.405	.016
PHE	<---	N	.358	.063	5.638	***
PHE	<---	SR	-.696	.063	-11.140	***
PHE	<---	ESC	.923	.079	11.743	***

Legend: P<.05 (***) is Significant and P>.05 Not Significant

Table 16. The Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Model 1 of Productivity

Variables	Direct	Indirect	Total Effects
Risk Management	0.055	0.000	0.055
Engagement	0.107	0.000	0.107
Evaluation	0.069	0.000	0.069
Culture	-0.093	0.000	-0.093
Facilitation	-0.027	0.000	-0.027
Performance Management	0.110	0.000	0.110
Nurturing Environment	0.257	0.000	0.257
Sense of Responsibility	-0.507	0.000	-0.507
Commitment to Lifelong Learning	0.535	0.000	0.535

Table 17. Standard of Fit Indices in Causal Model 1 of Productivity

Index	Standard Value Per Criterion	Value
CMIN/DF	<2.0	31.071
P-Value	>.05	0.000
NFI	>.95	0.069
TLI	>.95	-0.170
CFI	>.95	0.064
GFI	>.95	.300
RMSEA	<.05	.422

Table 18. *Regression Weights of Causal Model 2 of Productivity*

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
ESC	<---	RM	.025	.026	.943	.346
ESC	<---	EN	-.019	.037	-.513	.608
ESC	<---	EV	.021	.044	.484	.629
ESC	<---	CU	.056	.050	1.116	.265
ESC	<---	FA	.047	.056	.834	.405
ESC	<---	PM	-.101	.044	-2.301	.021
ESC	<---	N	.186	.045	4.168	***
ESC	<---	SR	.572	.044	12.854	***
PHE	<---	ESC	.633	.088	7.194	***

Legend: P<.05 (***) is Significant and P>.05 Not Significant

Table 19. *The Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Model 2 of Productivity*

Variables	Direct	Indirect	Total Effects
Risk Management	0.000	0.018	0.018
Engagement	0.000	-0.012	-0.012
Evaluation	0.000	0.013	0.013
Culture	0.000	0.031	0.031
Facilitation	0.000	0.027	0.027
Performance Management	0.000	-0.065	-0.065
Nurturing Environment	0.000	0.112	0.112
Sense of Responsibility	0.000	0.348	0.348
Commitment to Lifelong Learning	0.000	0.484	0.484

Table 20. *Standard of Fit Indices in Causal Model 2 of Productivity*

Index	Standard Value Per Criterion	Value
CMIN/DF	<2.0	4.792
P-Value	>.05	0.000
NFI	>.95	0.968
TLI	>.95	0.853
CFI	>.95	0.974
GFI	>.95	.961
RMSEA	<.05	.150

Table 21. *Regression Weights of Causal Model 3 of Productivity*

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
ESC	<---	PM	-.078	.040	-1.944	.052
ESC	<---	SR	.588	.043	13.645	***

ESC	<---	CU	.081	.041	2.008	.045
ESC	<---	N	.179	.042	4.265	***
PHE	<---	ESC	.947	.176	5.379	***
PHE	<---	SR	-.678	.143	-4.735	***
PHE	<---	N	.304	.101	3.007	.003
PHE	<---	CU	-.139	.101	-1.370	.171
PHE	<---	EN	.177	.076	2.346	.019
PHE	<---	PM	.194	.094	2.057	.040

Legend: P<.05 (***) is Significant and P>.05 Not Significant

Table 22. The Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Model 3 of Productivity

Variables	Direct	Indirect	Total Effects
Engagement	0.181	0.000	0.181
Culture	-0.123	0.068	-0.055
Performance Management	0.196	-0.075	0.122
Nurturing Environment	0.288	0.160	0.448
Sense of Responsibility	-0.652	0.535	-0.117
Commitment to Lifelong Learning	0.724	0.000	0.724

Table 23. Standard of Fit Indices in Causal Model 3 of Productivity

Index	Standard Value Per Criterion	Value
CMIN/DF	<2.0	0.000
P-Value	>.05	0.989
NFI	>.95	1.000
TLI	>.95	1.028
CFI	>.95	1.000
GFI	>.95	1.000
RMSEA	<.05	0.000

For the first research question, all of the respondents’ perception on strategic planning in terms of risk management were highly influential, in general, having the highest mean of 4.453, an overall mean of 4.149, and standard deviation of 1.018, accordingly. All of the respondents’ perception on strategic planning in terms of engagement were highly influential, in general, having the highest mean of 4.600, an overall mean of 4.401, and standard deviation of 0.702, accordingly. All of the respondents’ perception on strategic planning in terms of evaluation were highly influential, in general, having the highest mean of 4.441, an overall mean of 4.352, and standard deviation of 0.655, accordingly.

For the second research question, all of the respondents’ perception on organizational learning in terms of culture were performed, in general, having the highest mean of 4.412, an overall mean of 4.228, and standard deviation of 0.639, accordingly. All of the respondents’ perception on organizational learning in terms of facilitation were performed, in general, having the highest mean of 4.318, an overall mean of 4.131, and standard deviation of 0.611, accordingly. All of the respondents’ perception on organizational learning in terms of performance management were performed, in general, having the highest mean of 4.424, an overall mean of 4.269, and standard deviation of 0.688, accordingly.

For the third research question, all of the respondents’ perception on school culture in terms of nurturing environment were engaged, in general, having the highest mean of 4.224, an overall mean of 4.082, and standard deviation of 0.621, accordingly. All of the respondents’ perception on school culture in terms of sense of responsibility were engaged, in general, having the highest mean of

4.654, an overall mean of 4.278, and standard deviation of 0.650, accordingly. All of the respondents' perception on school culture in terms of commitment to lifelong learning were engaged, in general, having the highest mean of 4.318, an overall mean of 4.152, and standard deviation of 0.523, accordingly.

For the fourth research question, all of the respondents' perception on productivity in terms of leadership were highly productive, in general, having the highest mean of 4.512, an overall mean of 4.313, and standard deviation of 1.096, accordingly. All of the respondents' perception on productivity in terms of capacity resources were highly productive, in general, having the highest mean of 4.235, an overall mean of 4.131, and standard deviation of 0.516, accordingly.

For the fifth research question, the respondents' perception exposed that productivity has a significant positive relationship with all the independent variables such as school culture, organizational learning, and strategic planning. The p-value is <0.001 , therefore, the null hypothesis has been rejected.

For the sixth research question, the multiple regression analysis revealed one of the independent and observed variables are positively correlated and statistically significant where probability value of $p=0.000$ ($F=11.357$) indicates that there was a significant relationship between the HEIs' productivity, and the predictor variables. Nine variables included in the model, risk management ($p>.05$), engagement ($p>.05$), evaluation ($p>.05$), culture ($p>.05$), facility ($p>.05$), and performance management ($p>.05$) statistically failed to predict/influenced the productivity of higher education institutions. The variables that best predicts/influences productivity of higher education institutions are nurturing environment, $p = <.05$, $t = 3.243$, $\beta = 339$, sense of responsibility, $p = <.05$, $t = -4.734$, $\beta = -669$, and commitment to lifelong learning, $p = <.05$, $t = 5.102$, $\beta = .706$). According to the findings, the productivity of higher education institutions is greatly influenced by the school culture, which involves adaptation, integration, sharing, and learning of the stakeholders.

In problem 7, the study employed causal modelling and path analysis to develop a casual model for the performance of the service providers. The results revealed that the Hypothesized Model 3, incorporating the variables namely; engagement, culture, performance management, nurturing environment, sense of responsibility, and commitment to lifelong learning in the model and the productivity of private higher education institutions, was one of the best-fitting models based on the goodness-of-fit indices. The chi-square to degrees of freedom ratio (CMIN/DF) of 0.000 is below the threshold of 2.00, indicating a good fit. The p-value of 0.989 is greater than 0.05, suggesting that the model is not significantly different from the observed data. Additionally, the GFI, NFI, TLI, and CFI indices exceed the standard value of 0.95, indicating a good fit. The root mean squared error approximation (RMSEA) value of 0.000 is below the cutoff 0.05, further supporting the model's goodness-of-fit.

Conclusions

The study came to the conclusion that there is a significant relationship that exists between the productivity of private higher education institutions and the independent variables. This indicates that the productivity of private higher education institutions is significantly correlated with school culture. Yet, this still implies that the productivity increases as school culture, strategic planning, and organizational learning increase.

Among the three (3) independent variables, school culture strongly correlates with productivity of private higher education institutions. The statements of the respondents on the level of school culture conclude that the lifelong learning, nurturing, and sense of being responsible approach plays an important role in the educational institutions and has emerged as a research subject which requires detailed examination.

The best fit model 3, considering the variables such as strategic planning (particularly engagement), organizational learning (particularly culture and performance management), and school culture (particularly nurturing environment, sense of responsibility, and commitment to lifelong learning) emerges as the most influential factors for boosting increasing the productivity of the private higher educational institutions in Cagayan de Oro City.

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